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The Role of the Construction Industry in the Global Economy and its Management Organization Features

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Abstract: *The construction industry is a vital sector of the global economy, playing a significant role in the development and growth of countries. It is a complex and multifaceted industry, covering a wide range of activities, including the construction of buildings, infrastructure and industrial facilities. The construction industry makes a significant contribution to the global economy by providing employment opportunities, generating income and stimulating economic growth. In this article, we will consider the role of the construction industry in the global economy and consider the features of its management organization.*

Key words: *construction industry, global sectors, employment in construction, future changes, new opportunities.*

Introduction

Construction is one of the most dynamic and responsive sectors in the industry. It is also highly productive and drives significant economic growth due to the inter-sectoral linkages between construction and other sectors, making the construction sector a powerful force in the economy. The construction industry makes significant contributions to sustainable economic development by achieving some of the key development goals, including increasing economic output, creating jobs, and generating and redistributing income. It also plays an important role in meeting basic physical and social needs, including the construction of housing, infrastructure, and consumer goods. Therefore, it is very important to know how the construction sector responds to changes in other aspects of the economy. Previous studies have shown that there is a positive relationship between construction output and economic growth, especially in developing countries. Therefore, it is important to understand the contribution of the construction sector to socio-economic development and economic growth.

Literature Review

The construction industry plays a key role in the global economy, characterized by its unique characteristics that influence and are influenced by various global trends. The study of this industry reveals significant changes and challenges, especially in the context of globalization and technological advances.

In the seminal work of Ernur Akiner (2009), the authors highlight the profound impact of globalization on the construction sector. They argue that the development of the industry is characterized by increased competition and the need for innovative solutions to reduce costs and improve efficiency. The study emphasizes that successful project execution in a global environment goes beyond technical knowledge and requires an understanding of cultural, political and legal barriers. This multifaceted approach to project management is critical as construction firms navigate the complexities of international operations, especially in joint ventures with local partners.

Building on this foundation, Nogueiro et al. (2011) expand the field by examining the role of the construction industry in socio-economic development, particularly in relation to the United Nations Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Their study highlights the multiplier effect of the construction sector on employment and its critical contribution to infrastructure development, which is essential to achieving broader economic and social goals. The study illustrates the relationship between a country's stage of development and its construction activity, providing insights into growth strategies adapted to different economic contexts, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Foley, P. (2018) further contributes to understanding productivity in the construction industry by highlighting the challenges of measuring productivity across regions. His comparative analysis shows that while technological advances and globalization may improve productivity, macroeconomic analysis often casts doubt on the sector's growth trajectory. Foley's findings suggest that definitions of productivity vary and that improving productivity remains a critical challenge for companies seeking to optimize their financial performance.

Ngor K. et al. (2019) study materials management, identifying critical factors affecting project success for contractors of different sizes. Their study highlights that effective materials management is vital for all contractors, especially the small and medium-sized enterprises that dominate the construction market. Despite their significant contributions to the industry, these smaller organizations have been largely overlooked in the literature, highlighting a research gap that needs to be addressed to improve overall project performance. Lovrenčić Butković and Mihic (2019) analyze internationalization trends in the construction sector, with a particular focus on Croatian companies. They argue that effective

project management is essential for construction firms to thrive in the face of competitive pressures and changing market demands. Their findings indicate that technology adoption and strategic planning are critical to addressing the complex challenges of the industry, driven by factors such as urbanization and public infrastructure projects. The authors point out the slow pace of technology adoption in the industry, which is exacerbated by a lack of innovation and skilled labour.

Overall, the literature highlights the important role of the construction industry in the global economy and reveals the multifaceted challenges it faces in terms of management and organizational practices. These findings provide a foundation for a more in-depth examination of the industry's dynamics and the strategies firms use to adapt and thrive in an increasingly complex environment.

Recommendations

The construction industry makes a significant contribution to the global economy, accounting for a significant portion of global GDP. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), the construction industry accounts for about 6% of global GDP, with annual industry revenues exceeding \$10 trillion. The industry provides employment opportunities to millions of people around the world, and the ILO estimates that it employs more than 270 million people worldwide. The construction industry is also an important contributor to economic growth, as the output of the industry has a multiplier effect on the economy. One of the most important roles of the construction industry is in infrastructure development. The construction industry is responsible for the construction of roads, bridges, airports, and other critical infrastructure that is essential for economic growth and development. The industry also plays a critical role in the construction of housing and commercial buildings that provide housing and jobs for individuals and businesses [1]. In addition, the construction industry is also involved in the construction of industrial facilities such as manufacturing plants and power plants, which are critical to the growth and development of industries. In addition to its economic importance, the construction industry also plays a vital role in social and environmental sustainability. The industry is responsible for the development of green buildings and sustainable infrastructure, which reduces carbon emissions and promotes environmental sustainability. The industry also plays a vital role in supporting social sustainability by providing affordable housing and public facilities, which promote social cohesion and overcome inequality.

Despite its importance, the construction industry also faces several challenges, including a shortage of skilled labor, inadequate infrastructure, and environmental degradation. The industry is also facing increasing pressure to adopt sustainable practices and reduce its environmental impact. To address these challenges, the industry must adopt effective management practices that prioritize sustainability, quality, and safety. Within the construction industry, the building construction category holds the largest market share and its revenue is projected to grow steadily over the forecast period. Revenue in the building construction market is projected to increase as the world becomes increasingly urbanized and more people and businesses require buildings. With rising per capita wealth in developing countries, the commercial sector is expanding, allowing for increased spending on commercial building construction. Revenue growth in the heavy and civil construction industry is expected to be steady over the forecast period. The heavy and civil construction industry is growing due to increased government spending on infrastructure as a result of continued economic growth in developing countries. Automation and Internet of Things (IoT) in construction equipment are increasing the demand for better and faster infrastructure construction, which is likely to drive revenue growth in the building construction market. With increasing knowledge about the optimal use of resources and adherence to stringent environmental regulations during construction projects and operations, the land development segment is expected to account for the largest share of revenue during the forecast period

[3-4]. The growing need to gain access to factors that may impact the properties under construction in the future, such as future property values or availability of natural resources to support construction, is driving the growth of the land development segment in the future. The global building construction market is segmented into two types of buildings: residential and non-residential. The residential building category is expected to generate the highest revenue during the forecast period. The residential building segment is projected to grow as the demand for residential housing increases coupled with rising disposable income in certain regions. In addition, the residential property category is growing due to the growing preference for homes with lower carbon footprint and eco-friendliness. As a result of the growing trend of modernization in developing countries, many young people are seeking to own their own homes, which will contribute to the growth of income in the housing segment in the future. The reduction in mortgage interest rates is another aspect that is expected to increase the demand for new housing units in the future.

Мировой рынок строительной отрасли, 2020-2029 гг., в млрд долл. США

Table 1

Effective management is critical to the success of construction projects, which are complex and multifaceted. Construction project management involves several key stakeholders, including project owners, contractors, architects, and engineers. The management process typically includes several stages, including project planning, implementation, and closure. During the project planning stage, stakeholders define project objectives, define project requirements, and establish project timelines and budgets. During the project execution stage, stakeholders implement project plans, manage project risks, and monitor project progress. During the project completion stage, stakeholders evaluate project results, identify lessons learned, and document project outcomes. Several management systems and tools are used to effectively manage projects in the construction industry. One of the most commonly used platforms is the Project Management Institute (PMI), which provides a structured approach to project management. The PMI system includes five process groups, including initiating, planning, executing, monitoring and controlling, and closing. The system also includes several knowledge areas including integration management, scope management, time management, cost management, quality

management, resource management, communication management, risk management and procurement management.

Another widely used system in the construction industry is the lean construction system, which is based on the principles of lean manufacturing. The lean construction system aims to minimize waste, maximize value, and optimize project workflows. This framework includes several key principles, including value definition, value stream mapping, future state creation, and future state realization. Several project management tools and techniques are also used in the construction industry to effectively manage projects. One of the most commonly used tools is the Gantt chart, which provides a visual representation of the project time frame. The Gantt chart is used to schedule project tasks, allocate resources, and track the progress of the project. Another widely used tool is the critical path method (CPM), which is used to identify the most important tasks of a project and allocate resources accordingly. In addition to these tools and techniques, the construction industry is also adopting several innovative technologies, including building information modeling (BIM) and big data analytics. BIM is a digital representation of the physical and functional characteristics of a building that is used to plan, design, and manage construction projects. Big data analytics is the process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting large amounts of data to gain insights and make informed decisions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the construction industry plays a vital role in the global economy by providing employment opportunities, generating income and driving economic growth. The industry also makes a significant contribution to social and environmental sustainability by developing green buildings and sustainable infrastructure. Despite its importance, the industry also faces a number of challenges including a shortage of skilled labor, inadequate infrastructure and environmental degradation. To address these challenges, the industry must implement effective management practices that prioritize sustainability, quality and safety. The adoption of innovative technologies such as BIM and big data analytics are also critical to the success of construction projects. By adopting these innovative technologies and effective management practices, the construction industry can continue to play a vital role in the global economy and support sustainable development.

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